

A comparative analysis of small-scale octopus value chains in Latin America.

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Abstract

Octopus small-scale fisheries are a highly important economic and subsistence activity, being a source of income and food security for several coastal communities worldwide, especially for women, that can operate in one or several nodes of the value chains. In general, small-scale octopus fisheries do not require expensive investments with fishing gears and other materials. Additionally, these fisheries generally operate with a targeted species, have low unintentional catches and do not cause widespread seabed damage, which is a strong stand from the sustainability perspective. Despite its significant importance and increasing market demand, little information is available about octopus value chains and trade interactions worldwide. In this study, we will contrast and discuss the characteristics and operations of three diverse octopus small-scale fisheries in different countries in Latin America: Mexico, Brazil and Chile. These fisheries vary regarding the target species, fishing method and fishing gear; environmental, social, economic, cultural and institutional contexts; contribution to local communities and/or global markets. We will provide a general understanding on key aspects of each of these fisheries, explore governance aspects related to management and decision-making processes and give an overview of the participation of women in the octopus value chains. Finally, we will explore the main challenges faced by these fisheries and opportunities that could improve octopus value chain efficiency, sustainability and cause positive socio-economic impacts for the local communities.

